

CITIZENS' ASSEMBLY REPORT ZHYTOMYR 2025

Transport Infrastructure and Sustainable Mobility

October 25–26 and November 1–2, 2025

Group discussions during the citizens' assembly, Zhytomyr, 1 November 2025
Photo: Ihor Kostash

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Kyiv School of Economics, Kyiv, 2026

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS USED IN THE REPORT:

SUMP	Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan
KSE	Kyiv School of Economics
Public advisor	participant in the citizens' assembly

The voting process on the fourth day of the citizens' assembly, 2 November, 2025, Zhytomyr. Photo: Ihor Kostash

INTRODUCTION

Cooperation between the Zhytomyr city council and the BRIDGE project resulted in the city's first citizens' assembly. The assembly focused on sustainable mobility and the development of transport infrastructure. It took place from 25 October to 2 November 2025. It represented the first instance in Zhytomyr of the application of contemporary deliberative democracy methods, including the involvement of citizens randomly selected and informed discussion in small groups (deliberation).

Methodological compliance and the quality of preparation and moderation were ensured by experts from the BRIDGE project at the Kyiv School of Economics (KSE) and the Technical University of Berlin (TU Berlin).

Sixty-four public advisers participated in the assembly. They were randomly selected residents of Zhytomyr, representing different age groups, professions, and areas of the city. Participants also reflected a diversity of everyday mobility patterns, including car owners, public transport users, cyclists and those who primarily travel on foot. This approach ensured that a broad range of perspectives and experiences was represented and created the conditions for meaningful dialogue between citizens, experts and city officials.

The assembly aimed to develop fair, realistic and balanced recommendations on how to make movement around the city safer, more convenient and more accessible for all population groups. Over four intensive days, participants reviewed expert materials, worked in small groups, analysed examples from Ukrainian and European cities, and collectively sought solutions to the current challenges facing Zhytomyr in the field of urban mobility.

The agenda and content of the discussions were based on previous surveys of the public and relevant officials, requests from the Transport and Communications Department of the Zhytomyr city council, and current strategic documents approved by the Zhytomyr community. These documents govern the field of urban mobility. Foremost among these is the Zhytomyr Sustainable Mobility Plan, developed and approved in 2019, which establishes the framework for the development of sustainable mobility in the city. The plan defines key directions for the development of public transport, cycling infrastructure, road safety, pedestrianisation, and other related components. In 2024, the community also adopted the Concept for the Development of Cycling Infrastructure in the Zhytomyr City Territorial Community, which outlines specific routes and standards for their implementation.

The assembly focused on key aspects of urban mobility that shape the everyday experience of getting around Zhytomyr. Participants addressed issues related to traffic safety and parking organisation in the city centre and residential areas, approaches to pedestrianisation and the development of cycling infrastructure, as well as the challenges and opportunities associated with public transport.

As a result of their joint efforts, participants compiled a list of recommendations, assessed their importance and feasibility, and voted on those proposals that could be implemented within the next one to two years. A total of 19 recommendations were put to the vote, of which 14 received the support of the Assembly and were identified as priority actions.

The citizens' assembly in Zhytomyr was held as part of the BRIDGE research project, with financial support from the European Union (Horizon Europe programme, project No. 101160337). The recommendations and experience gained through the process will make an important contribution to the development of democratic participatory practices and urban mobility planning in Ukrainian communities. The recommendations were submitted to the Zhytomyr city council in November 2025 for consideration as part of the 2026 budget process.

Group photo of participants in the citizens' assembly, 2 November 2025, Zhytomyr
Photo: Ihor Kostash

ASSEMBLY PARTICIPANTS

Participants in the citizens' assembly were selected in two stages through a random selection method. In the first stage (August–September 2025), 2,550 invitations were sent to randomly selected addresses from the list of all addresses served by Zhytomyrvodokanal, ensuring an even distribution across the city's districts and the village of Veresy. Two-thirds of the participants were randomly selected from among those who responded positively to the invitation.

In the second stage (September 2025), registration for participation in the citizens' assembly was opened to all interested individuals. A further third of the participants were selected by random selection from the submitted applications. As a result of this process, 90 individuals were invited to participate in the assembly. The Technical University of Berlin conducted both random selection processes. A dedicated stratified selection algorithm ensured that the composition of the assembly closely approximated proportional representation of residents by age, gender, and area of residence, and took into account the diversity of transport modes within the city.

On the first day of the assembly, 64 residents of Zhytomyr participated; on the second and third days, there were 63 participants; and on the fourth day, 61 participants took part. As a result of the efforts made, the majority of participants (58%) were individuals invited during the first stage.

The distribution of participants by age group and gender is presented below:

Table 1. Distribution of participants in the citizens' assembly by age group and gender.

Age	Total	Men	Women
≤25	9	6	3
26–35	5	2	3
36–43	13	3	10
44–59	21	6	15
60+	16	8	8
Total:	64	25	39

During the selection of participants, the algorithm was designed to ensure proportional representation of residents from all parts of Zhytomyr, as well as from the village of Veresy. This made it possible to include participants living in different areas of the city who face diverse challenges when travelling around it. The table below shows the number of representatives from each area.

Table 2. Distribution of participants in the citizens' assembly by area of residence

Area	Number of participants	Area	Number of participants
Centre	23	Maliiovanka	2
Bohuniia	12	Marianivka	1
Vokzal	3	Polova	4
Korbutivka	6	Village of Veresy	3
Koroliovskyyi	2	Other	5
Kroshnia	3		

Among the 64 participants in the assembly, 26 indicated that they own a car. Forty-seven participants reported that they regularly use public transport, 12 of whom also own a car. Thirteen participants reported that they often travel by bicycle (five of whom own a car, and nine of whom mainly use public transport). In addition, 30 participants reported that they typically or primarily travel around the city on foot.

The level of education and type of professional activity also constituted an important dimension of diversity among the assembly participants. The data presented in Tables 3 and 4 demonstrate the broad representation of different educational and professional groups among the public advisors. Participants with higher education are slightly overrepresented compared with Ukraine as a whole. In Ukraine, 55% of the workforce aged 15–70 has higher education. This diversity was essential in creating a space in which different experiences, perspectives, and understandings of the city’s challenges could be heard.

Table 3. Distribution of participants in the citizens’ assembly by level of education.

Level of education	Number of participants	% of participants
Basic general secondary	1	2 %
Vocational (technical) education	5	14 %
Professional pre-higher education	5	8 %
Complete general secondary	9	8 %
Higher education	44	69 %

Table 4. Distribution of participants in the citizens’ assembly by type of employment (some participants reported more than one type of employment).

Type of employment	Number of participants	Type of employment	Number of participants
Parental leave	1	Education professional	5
Homeowners' association chair (OSBB)	3	Self-employed (e.g. sole trader / individual entrepreneur)	11
Healthcare professional	3	Student	12
Civil servant or local government official	4	Employed in another sector	12
Temporarily not employed	5	Retired	15

Participants in the citizens' assembly*

No.	Surname	First name	No.	First name	Ім'я
1	Baranovska	Iryna	33	Merimskyi	Yevhen
2	Bychkov	Danylo	34	Milenko	Larisa
3	Bilousov	Pavlo	35	Momot	Tetiana
4	Biliai	Olena	36	Novitska	Inesa
5	Brokariiev	Viktor	37	Panchenko	Liudmyla
6	Brokariieva	Viktoriiia	38	Pavlenko	Oleksandr
7	Bialkovska	Tetiana	39	Pavlik	Olha
8	Vintskovska	Тетяна	40	Podorozhna	Svitlana
9	Vitkovskyi	Myroslav	41	Polishchuk	Diana
10	Holembiovskyi	Valentyn	42	Potapchuk	Olha
11	Honcharova	Yuliia	43	Prylutskyi	Ihor
12	Hordiichuk	Olha	44	Pryshchepa	Mariia
13	Hryhorovych	Iryna	45	Pustovoit	Olha
14	Hrytsenko	Oksana	46	Rybachuk	Mykhailo
15	Hubar	Vitalii	47	Ryzhkova	Taisiia
16	Humeniuk	Inna	48	Romanova	Inna
17	Dvorska	Anna	49	Rudik	Oleksandr
18	Dzhemula	Serhii	50	Sakhno	Mykola
19	Diatel	Yaroslav	51	Skorokhod	Vladyslav
20	Zabrodska	Anastasia	52	Smirnova	Iryna
21	Zahurska-Antoniuk	Viktoriiia	53	Stasenko	Oleksandr
22	Zelinskyi	Ruslan	54	Tarasiuk	Olha
23	Kovalova	Tetiana	55	Trokhymyshyn	Serhii
24	Kovalchuk	Svitlana	56	Franchuk	Viktoriiia
25	Komareus	Tetiana	57	Khodorovska	Iryna
26	Kos	Danylo	58	Chorny	Taras
27	Kravchuk	Ruslan	59	Shafir	Yevhen
28	Kukharska	Lesia	60	Shpakivska	Hanna

No.	Surname	First name	No.	First name	Ім'я
29	Miaka	Yadviha	61	Shustova	Mariia
30	Mazur	Serhii	62	Yanushevych	Tetiana
31	Mareieva	Tetiana	63	Yashchenko	Yurii
32	Melai	Vitalii			

*1 participant did not consent to having their name included in this list.

“Overall, in my experience, this is the best format, as it brings together a wide range of people of different ages and with different views. Through this process, we can arrive at the best solution democratically.”

*Assembly participant, **Serhii Dzhemula***

Final voting of the citizens' assembly,
2 November 2025, Zhytomyr.
Photo: Ihor Kostash

VOTED AND ADOPTED RECOMMENDATIONS

RECOMMENDATIONS APPROVED BY VOTING

(Recommendations assessed as feasible for implementation within one to two years were put to the vote).

● % of votes in favour

SAFETY

- 1. Implement at least one completed cycling route in accordance with the cycling concept.**

91%

Note

Throughout the citizens' assembly, cycling infrastructure remained highly relevant and was the focus of much of the discussion. When priorities were set, it received the highest number of votes among the topics considered. During the educational component of the assembly, public advisors were presented with cycling routes developed as part of the Concept for the Development of the City's Cycling Infrastructure, adopted by the Zhytomyr city council in 2024. In total, the document provides for 15 urban cycling routes connecting different parts of the city. This recommendation concerns the implementation of these urban cycling routes. Participants also discussed current challenges in implementing the cycling concept with experts, met with representatives of the cycling community, and highlighted the lack of a systematic approach to the development of cycling infrastructure. Among other proposals, ideas for the standardisation of cycle path design and development were considered.

- 2. Ensure the uninterrupted operation of traffic lights, including through the provision of alternative power supplies (e.g. solar panels).**

98%

- 3. Extend the duration of green traffic light signals for pedestrians on wide roads and install safety islands.**

93%

Note

During discussions on safety when travelling around the city, public advisors identified dangerous crossings on wide streets. In particular, they noted that the duration of the pedestrian green signal was insufficient. An excessively short green signal creates additional risks, particularly for people with limited mobility, who may not have sufficient time to complete the crossing safely. The lack of appropriate road markings and traffic-calming measures, which further increase the danger at such crossings, was also noted.

- 4. Ensure effective quality control of road works through public involvement, and hold the contracting authority and the contractor accountable for any violations.**

89%

Note

During the discussions, assembly participants repeatedly linked road safety issues to the poor quality of planning and execution of road works, as well as to the lack of effective oversight of their implementation. This is evident, in particular, in the poor condition of road surfaces and in repairs carried out without due regard for the approved principles of the Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP) and the cycling concept. During the training session, the example of Lutsk was presented, where a public organisation is involved in monitoring the quality of work and planning processes. During the discussions, public advisers (assembly participants) emphasised the need to hold officials accountable for violations occurring during the planning or repair of streets.

- 5. Improve control over the quality of lighting at pedestrian crossings.**

98%

- 6. The city should apply tactical traffic-calming measures, particularly during ongoing road works and in the vicinity of medical, social and educational facilities.**

86%

Note

During the discussions, citizens' advisers actively considered ways to improve pedestrian safety, particularly in areas with heavy traffic and near pedestrian crossings. Experts cited a range of approaches to addressing this issue, including behavioural methods that create conditions encouraging drivers to slow down, particularly when approaching pedestrian crossings. In the course of the discussions, practical solutions included the use of speed bumps, Berlin cushions, safety islands, appropriate road markings, and other measures.

PARKING

7. **Develop and implement paid parking on the central streets of Zhytomyr.** 82%
8. **Provide support to homeowners' associations (OSBBs) and housing cooperatives in the registration of adjacent land plots for their own needs, including parking facilities.** 70%

Note

Citizens' advisers discussed the need to create effective mechanisms for organising areas adjacent to residential buildings in response to the problem of chaotic parking in courtyards, the entry of unauthorised vehicles, and the displacement of pedestrians from courtyard spaces. During the expert sessions, examples were presented of homeowners' associations registering adjacent areas for long-term use and organising courtyard spaces with clearly defined zones and controlled parking. Citizens' advisers viewed this approach as a tool for returning courtyards to residents and reducing conflicts between pedestrians and drivers

9. **Install parking meters offering cashless and cash payment options, and develop a dedicated mobile application featuring a parking map with information on prices and parking availability.** 82%
10. **Introduce the impoundment of vehicles parked in violation of traffic regulations.** 68%

BICYCLES

11. **Based on the cycling concept, develop a phased plan to implement a unified network of continuous, safe cycle routes for bicycle and kick scooter users.** 75%

KYIVSKA STREET

12. **Refrain from introducing one-way traffic within the scope of the traffic management changes project between the intersection of Nebesna Sotnia Street and Skhidna Street, and instead optimise traffic signal operation and introduce dedicated left- and right-turn signals.** 67%

Note

The topic of traffic organisation on Kyivska Street was among the most frequently discussed during the assembly. The city council submitted for public discussion a draft amendment to the traffic organisation plan proposing the introduction of one-way traffic on the section between Nebesna Sotnia Street and Skhidna Street. The assembly primarily discussed changes that could be implemented as part of the current street repairs, in particular adjustments to the traffic management system, road markings, traffic signals, and the use of tactical traffic-calming measures. A significant part of the discussion was devoted to the need for professionally designed interventions on this street, with the involvement of relevant experts and broader public consultation. An alternative recommendation, which provided for the implementation of changes only on the condition of public and expert design with the involvement of the public, received 2% fewer votes and did not reach the required threshold of support. Therefore, it was not recommended. In addition, group discussions repeatedly emphasised the need for a systematic approach to changes in traffic organisation not only on Kyivska Street but also on adjacent streets, particularly in the event of introducing one-way traffic. Participants also expressed concern about the ineffectiveness and potential risks associated with the use of half-spheres as an anti-parking measure, particularly for people with visual impairments, and stressed the need to address the problem of parking on pavements.

13. **Review route duplication along Kyivska Street and ensure that priority is given to public transport.** 81%

PUBLIC TRANSPORT

14. **Develop an integrated single-ticket system for public transport operated by municipal and private entities, taking into account preferential fare categories for community residents, and ensure that the ticket is also available to non-residents.** 91%

REJECTED RECOMMENDATIONS

● % of votes in favour

SAFETY

1. **Address the issue of unregulated trading in pedestrian areas by engaging with sellers, informing them about opportunities to trade in available spaces, and strengthening control over the use of existing designated areas.**

65%

KYIVSKA STREET

2. **Increase the provision of green spaces on Kyivska street.**

47%

3. **Implement the project to change the traffic management system on Kyivska street only under the following conditions:**

39%

- 1) Test the proposed solution through both modelling and pilot implementation, and make a decision based on the results.
- 2) Optimise public transport routes to eliminate duplication.
- 3) Divert suburban transport away from Kyivska street to a bypass.
- 4) Increase the duration of pedestrian traffic light signals.
- 5) Implement cycling infrastructure on parallel streets.
- 6) Assess the impact of these changes on the overall traffic system of adjacent streets.

PUBLIC TRANSPORT

1. **Consider the allocation of separate lanes for public transport on Kyivska street.**

47%

2. **Relocate suburban public transport services outside the boundaries of Kyivska street.**

49%

RECOMMENDATIONS WITH AN IMPLEMENTATION TIMEFRAME OF MORE THAN THREE YEARS, NOT SUBMITTED TO A VOTE

(included in the report for the information of the city council and to reflect the course of the discussions)

SAFETY

1. **Ensure high-quality drainage in problem areas (Pokrovska, Hrushevskoho, Khlіbna, and Mykhailivska streets).**

Note

Participants considered various approaches to addressing issues related to water drainage. The idea of applying the “sponge city” approach to several streets experiencing water drainage issues – namely Pokrovska, Hrushevskoho, Mykhailivska and Khlіbna – was repeatedly raised and discussed.

2. **Consider the option of constructing underground car parks (with the possibility of using them as shelters) equipped with appropriate water drainage systems.**

PARKING

3. **Convert neglected municipal land plots into parking lots.**
4. **Introduce a combined payment system: the first 30 minutes are free with a prepayment; more than 30 minutes – full payment; from 4 hours – double rate; a separate night tariff – nominal fee.**
5. **During the construction of new buildings, create multi-level above-ground parking lots near the house; 1 apartment – 1 parking space for cars and bicycles.**
6. **Inventory land plots near buildings and develop technical documentation taking into account green zones, recreation areas, and parking lots; carry out work with the participation of the heads of condominium associations (OSBB) and upon residents' requests.**
7. **Create (protected) parking spaces for bicycles, particularly multi-level ones.**

KYIVSKA STREET

8. **Carry out a major overhaul of the bridge in the direction of Kyiv at the beginning of Kyivska Street.**

Note

During the discussions, the problem of city congestion with transit traffic was raised. As a proposal to solve this problem, participants discussed the idea of forming a bypass route around Zhytomyr along the path: Vysoka Pich, Troianiv, Dvirets.

PUBLIC TRANSPORT

9. **Ensure that all stops are equipped in accordance with established standards, including benches, shelters, lighting, timetables, route maps and rubbish bins.**

Group discussions during the citizens' assembly, 1 November 2025, Zhytomyr. Photo: Ihor Kostash

COURSE OF THE ASSEMBLY AND FEATURES OF THE FORMAT

Agenda:

Transport infrastructure and mobility were key topics of the assembly – a highly important but broad area. The agenda was structured around three main themes:

Within the focus topic of safety, participants discussed how changes to the urban environment can reduce the speed of private vehicles and, consequently, lower the number of road traffic casualties. They also considered the use of tactical measures to slow traffic and improve safety at complex intersections in the city.

The focus topic of balancing the interests of different mobility groups in the city included discussions on the development of cycling infrastructure, parking in the city centre and in the courtyards of multi-storey residential buildings, and pedestrian infrastructure.

Another important focus of the discussions was the concept of a project to change the traffic flow on a section of Kyivska street, from the intersection with Nebesna Sotnia street to the intersection with Skhidna street. The project concept was presented by the Transport and Communications Department of the Zhytomyr city council. The project concept envisaged the introduction of a one-way traffic zone and the allocation of dedicated lanes on both sides for the shared use of public transport and cyclists.

Within each topic, expert reports were presented, allowing issues to be examined from multiple perspectives. The assembly participants included representatives of various mobility groups, which helped to maintain a balance of perspectives and ensure that all viewpoints were represented.

Educational component

The format of citizens' assemblies includes a substantial educational component, consisting of expert presentations covering various aspects of the topic and contributions from representatives of different interest groups. Each set of one to three educational presentations was followed by small group discussions. The overall structure of the assembly was designed to include more educational sessions at the beginning and more group discussions towards the end. Similarly, discussion topics at the beginning of the assembly were mostly broad and open-ended, while those towards the end were more focused on developing specific recommendations. Each discussion concluded with a plenary session, during which small groups presented their findings and the proposals of all groups were publicly recorded.

Over the four days of the citizens' assembly, there were 17 expert presentations and one panel discussion (approximately nine hours of educational content), as well as nine group discussions and ten plenary sessions (approximately 11 hours devoted to discussions among participants).

Small group discussions

For each discussion, an algorithm formed groups of different participants, assigning them in random order based on their assigned numbers. This approach enabled participants to communicate and interact with a wider range of other participants.

Most discussions took place in small groups of five participants.

All but one of the discussions took place without formal moderation. However, eight facilitators were present during the assembly, assigned to two tables. They supported the discussions, moderated conflict situations when necessary, and clarified questions and discussion topics.

Developing recommendations

At each plenary session, following the discussions, a joint list of statements and recommendations was compiled, drawing on the work of all groups.

During breaks, these aggregated lists were displayed for prioritisation: each participant received two to three voting stickers and selected the statements they considered most important.

On the third day of the citizens' assembly, the lists of priority recommendations across three topics – safety of movement around the city, balance of interests among all road users, and sustainability of decisions – formed the basis for preparing the recommendations to be put to a vote.

Before the final vote, small-group participants, in discussion with representatives of the Advisory Committee, divided the recommendations into those that could be implemented within one to two years and those that would require three years or more. Recommendations for which at least half of the groups identified the shorter implementation timeframe were put to a vote. Recommendations requiring a longer timeframe were submitted separately to the Zhytomyr city council as long-term community needs.

Final vote on recommendations

The final vote took place on 2 November 2025.

Nineteen recommendations were selected for the vote, all of which were assessed as realistic for implementation within one to two years.

Public advisers could vote “for” or “against”, or abstain.

Fifty-seven of the 63 assembly participants took part in the final vote.

For a recommendation to be adopted, it had to receive a two-thirds majority of votes in favour. This corresponded to a threshold of 38 votes, or 67%. Recommendations that did not reach this threshold were considered rejected.

“This is my first time participating in such events, but I understand that it will not be the last. It is exciting and gives me optimism that we, as ordinary citizens, can influence the resolution of issues that are important to us and to the city. Perhaps in the future, these issues will also become priorities for our children.”

Svitlana Kovalchuk, participant in the citizens’ assembly

Report by Volodymyr Vakhitov,
25 October 2025, Zhytomyr
Photo: Ihor Kostash

EDUCATIONAL COMPONENT: EXPERT REPORTS AND DISCUSSION

The educational component provides participants in the citizens' assembly with the information necessary to develop a shared understanding of the topic and to engage in informed discussions. During the assembly in Zhytomyr, each expert presentation lasted approximately 15 minutes, followed by 10–15 minutes for questions from participants. This format helped to clarify key issues immediately, facilitate an understanding of different perspectives, and ensure a considered engagement with the topic.

Over the course of four days, there were 16 educational presentations and one panel discussion. Topics covered both practical and strategic aspects of urban mobility, including:

- **The budget process in Zhytomyr** and the spending restrictions affecting the implementation of infrastructure solutions

Speaker: Svitlana Olshanska, first deputy mayor of Zhytomyr

- **Behavioural science** and its application in street design and traffic safety improvement

Speaker: Volodymyr Vakhitov, director of the Institute of Behavioural Research and associate professor at American University Kyiv

- **Review of community strategic documents** in the field of mobility and the status of their implementation (Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP), Integrated Development Concept)

Speaker: Dmytro Tkachuk, expert on urban mobility and sustainable development (Zhytomyr Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan), former deputy mayor of Zhytomyr for transport

- **Presentation of the concept for changing traffic management on Kyivska street.** One of the key topics of discussion at the assembly was supplemented by a panel discussion with experts and the relevant deputy mayor of Zhytomyr.

Speaker: Volodymyr Shumlyakivskiy, PhD in technical sciences, associate professor, department of mechanical engineering and automotive transport, Zhytomyr Polytechnic State University (Research on Zhytomyr's public transport network in 2018 and 2022; development of the Zhytomyr Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan; cycling concept for the Zhytomyr United Territorial Community)

- **Parking:** technological solutions, regulation, and integration into residential and central urban spaces

Speaker 1: Ching Fu Chen, researcher and professor, department of transportation and communications management, National Cheng Kung University (Taiwan)

Speaker 2: Oleksandr Shevchuk, deputy mayor of Zhytomyr for executive bodies

Speaker 3: Valerii Pyndyk, chairman of the board, Association of homeowners' associations (OSBBs) of the Solomyanskyi district of Kyiv

- **Pedestrianisation of urban space,** superblocks, and international examples of comfortable pedestrian areas

Speaker: Jordi Marfà, architect, graduate of the Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC Barcelona), staff member of the urban strategy department of the municipality of Barcelona

- **Challenges for public transport** in Zhytomyr and opportunities for improvement

Speaker: Andrii Shayda, public activist in the field of urban mobility and public transport (Zhytomyr)

- **Ongoing street repairs** and the prioritisation of streets

Speaker 1: Mykola Yermakov, acting head of the transport and communications department of the Zhytomyr city council

Speaker 2: Dmytro Pavlov, acting director of the Zhytomyr city council road management utility company

- **Meeting with police** representatives on traffic safety and the approval of changes to traffic regulations

Speaker 1: Ruslan Khomych, head of the traffic safety department, Zhytomyr patrol police

Speaker 2: Iryna Sereda, commander of the Zhytomyr region patrol police battalion

- **Low-budget interventions** to improve safety (Tactical urbanism, temporary solutions, testing changes)

Speaker: Artem Poliukh, transport infrastructure and modelling specialist, street and road design engineer, safety inspection engineer

- **The needs of cyclists** and an overview of Zhytomyr's cycling concept

Speaker: Alina Kundich, representative of the Zhytomyr region cyclists association, expert on school mobility, coordinator of the national campaign "Cycling to School"

Together, these presentations provided an information base that participants could draw on during further group discussions and the development of recommendations. The training component was designed to provide balanced access to different perspectives, both expert and user.

"I am simply delighted with the team that organised this event – from the level of expertise of those who spent four days informing us about various aspects of transport mobility, how these issues can be addressed in our city, and the experiences of other cities around the world."

Iryna Smirnova, participant in the citizens' assembly

Stakeholder Forum,
19 July 2025, Zhytomyr
Photo: Ihor Kostash

PREPARING THE CITIZENS' ASSEMBLY

April 2025

Informational events about citizens' assemblies in Zviahel, Chernihiv, Kyiv, and online

July 2025

- Stakeholder Forum
- Selection of the assembly topic
- Selection of the Advisory Committee

September 2025

Registration of interest open to all residents wishing to participate in the assembly

October–November 2025

Holding the citizens' assembly: 25-26 October and 01-02 November

February 2026

Official ceremony for handing over the report at the Zhytomyr City Council session

2027

Zhytomyr City Council report on the implementation of the assembly's recommendations

May 2025

- Competition for holding a citizens' assembly
- Win of the Zhytomyr Community

August 2025

2,055 invitation letters sent to randomly selected Vodokanal customers

October 2025

- Launch of online discussions on mobility via Polis
- Random selection of 92 Zhytomyr residents invited to the assembly

November 2025 – January 2026

- Recommendations officially submitted to the Zhytomyr City Council
- Preparation of the citizens' assembly report

2026–2027

Conducting scientific research and analysis based on the Zhytomyr experience

The citizens' assembly in Zhytomyr was the third citizens' assembly in Ukraine and the first to be held in a regional centre. Preparations began with a competition organised by the BRIDGE project among communities in the Kyiv, Chernihiv, and Zhytomyr regions to host the assembly. The first step involved informational events in these regions, held in person on 8, 9 and 10 April and online on 30 April. Applications from communities in these regions were accepted until 19 May. The application submitted by the Zhytomyr city community received the highest rating from a commission composed of representatives of the member universities of the BRIDGE project consortium (Kyiv School of Economics, Technical University of Berlin, the University of Tartu, and Erasmus University).

On 2 June, the first meeting with representatives of the Zhytomyr community was held to discuss preparations for the assembly. On behalf of the Zhytomyr city council, this process was organised by teams from the municipal institution Institute for City Development and the Public Relations Department. It was supported by the Secretary of the Zhytomyr city council, Halyna Shymanska, the First Deputy Mayor, Svitlana Olshanska, and the Deputy Mayor for Executive Bodies, Oleksandr Shevchuk.

The first public step was the Stakeholder Forum, held in Zhytomyr on 19 July 2025. The event brought together representatives of 29 public organisations, businesses, religious organisations, and educational institutions in the city. The forum aimed to select a topic for the assembly. Three topics proposed by the city council were put forward for discussion by the community:

01

Construction of a crematorium and burial culture

02

Sustainable housing policy of the Zhytomyr community

03

Transport infrastructure and sustainable mobility

Table 5. Participants in the Stakeholder Forum and the organizations they represented*.

No.	Surname	Name	Organisation
1	Barakh	Yevhenii	LLC GREEN BIN UKRAINE
2	Baranov	Ihor	Lyceum No. 23 of Zhytomyr named after M. Ocheret
3	Bashynska	Svitlana	Veterans' Home public union
4	Bohinska	Veronika	Separate branch of the NGO Ukrainian Students' Association in Zhytomyr Region
5	Borshchivskyi	Viktor	Medibor Clinic
6	Dankevych	Vitalii	Polissia National University
7	Deshkov	Maksym	Youth Council under the Zhytomyr city council / NGO Barrier-Free Community
8	Didenko	Volodymyr	Zhytomyr Regional NGO Kremenetskyi Foundation
9	Hladka	Iryna	NGO Myr na doloni, city council member
10	Horai	Oleh	City council member
11	Hulia	Yuliia	Business UStore Space
12	Isaiev	Andrii	Olimp Digital IT company
13	Isakov	Vadym	YaMariupol. Zhytomyr
14	Kovalchuk	Veronika	Zhytomyr city council

No.	Surname	Name	Organisation
15	Kulikov	Oleksandr	Great Translation Agency
16	Kyrychuk	Halyna	Zhytomyr Ivan Franko State University
17	Lozynska	Kateryna	Plast Youth Centre of the Zhytomyr city council
18	Luska	Oleh	Charity Foundation Caritas–Zhytomyr
19	Nikitich	Tetiana	LLC TD “Zhytomyr Sweets”
20	Onatskyi	Kyrylo	NGO Zhytomyr Enthusiasts
21	Plokhotniuk	Tetiana	NGO Peace Winds Japan
22	Poliakov	Oleksii	Military chaplain, volunteer
23	Polynovska	Mariia	NGO Zhytomyr Enthusiasts
24	Pylypchuk	Iryna	Lyceum No. 23
25	Rakovych	Oleksandr	City council member
26	Sheliahina	Daria	LLC GREEN BIN UKRAINE
27	Shumliakivskyi	Volodymyr	Zhytomyr Polytechnic State University
28	Soloviova	Zhanna	Zhytomyr Community Foundation
29	Vashchenko	Oleh	Lyceum No. 30 of Zhytomyr
30	Yatsyk	Iryna	Youth Foundation for European Initiatives
31	Yevmenchuk	Olha	NGO Zhytomyr Enthusiasts
32	Zhuravska	Oksana	City council member, lyceum director

*1 participant did not consent to having their name included in this list.

After discussions and voting, the topic “Transport infrastructure and sustainable mobility” won by a very small margin, with “Sustainable housing policy of the Zhytomyr community” coming in second place.

Preparation of the assembly agenda

To prepare the agenda, the BRIDGE project team studied existing strategic documents in the field of mobility in Zhytomyr and conducted focus groups with representatives of the public and relevant representatives of the Zhytomyr city council.

What documents are already available in the community?

- Integrated Urban Development Concept for Zhytomyr 2030 (2019).
- Zhytomyr Sustainable Mobility Plan (2019).
- Concept for the Development of Cycling Infrastructure in the Zhytomyr City Territorial Community (2024).

The city's sustainable mobility plan sets out the following priorities for the development of mobility in Zhytomyr:

1. Strengthening the role of public transport.
2. Traffic safety.
3. Encouraging walking.
4. Cycling.
5. Organising parking spaces.
6. External transport links to the city.

During August – September 2025, two focus groups were held with members of the public involved in mobility-related issues. Two focus groups were held with representatives of the Transport and Communications Department of the Zhytomyr city council and the relevant Deputy Mayor.

The public identified the following key areas of concern related to mobility:

- Ensuring inclusive and equitable travel conditions for vulnerable road users, including people with reduced mobility, children, pedestrians, and cyclists.
- Traffic safety, including road markings, traffic restrictions and dangerous intersections.
- Insufficient communication regarding the implementation of the Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP) and limited opportunities for public participation in infrastructure decision-making.
- Shortcomings in the functioning of public transport, including vehicle conditions, route coverage and the limited number of dedicated public transport lanes.
- Parking.

Representatives of the city council identified the following priority areas for discussion:

- Parking: residents' reluctance to introduce paid parking in the city centre and the problem of chaotic parking in courtyards.
- Traffic safety: reducing the speed of private vehicles and an experimental concept for changes to the traffic light system on Kyivska street.
- Public transport.
- Pilot projects in line with the Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP).
- Public engagement.

The results of the focus groups and the proposed agenda items were discussed with the Advisory Committee to more clearly define the key issues for the upcoming assembly.

Polis – online discussion on mobility in Zhytomyr

The BRIDGE project team, in collaboration with the Zhytomyr city council, launched an online discussion on transport infrastructure and mobility on the Polis platform on 10 October 2025. All city residents could log on to the platform, vote on statements (by selecting “agree” or “disagree”) or choose to “skip” them, as well as submit their own statements, which subsequent users could engage with through voting. [The Polis platform](#) enables the visualization of levels of support and opposition to statements, thereby providing insight into the presence or absence of conflict around individual issues. The results of the discussion were presented at the assembly to inform the participants.

Some statistics on the discussion on the Polis platform:

790

users participated
in the online
discussion

23 769

votes were
cast

162

participants
submitted
comments

265

comments
(statements) were
submitted in total

The report on statements relevant to the topic of the assembly is available on the Polis platform here:

“This is my first time participating in this format, and I find it very engaging. It is encouraging to see that public opinion has a place in our society, and I hope that the authorities will listen to it.”

Taras Chornyj, participant in the citizens' assembly

**ЗАПРОШЕННЯ
НА ГРОМАДСЬКУ АСАМБЛЕЮ**

Це міжнародний формат залучення мешканців до вирішення місцевих проблем і вироблення рекомендацій міській владі.
У цьому листі, як долучитися, щоб бути почутим.

Invitation letter during the selection of participants
for the citizens' assembly, August 2025
Photo: Zhytomyr City Council

FORMATION OF THE ASSEMBLY AND SELECTION OF THE TOPIC

Between 19 and 28 August, 2,550 physical invitation letters were sent to addresses randomly selected in the city of Zhytomyr and the village of Veresy. Residents at these addresses were invited to pre-register for participation in the citizens' assembly.

On 16 September, the Zhytomyr city council announced on social media that registration for the citizens' assembly was open to all interested individuals. This information was subsequently shared by local news portals and active citizens.

Zhytomyr residents invited to register for the first citizens' assembly

Registration remained open until 2 October 2025. As a result of the invitation campaign, 208 registrations were received, including 138 submitted via an online form and 70 by telephone. Experts from the Technical University of Berlin applied a stratified selection algorithm to identify 118 potential participants for the assembly. The aim was to achieve a composition that closely reflected the city's population in terms of age, gender, area of residence, and preferred modes of transport.

On the eve of the assembly, 84 participants were registered and confirmed by telephone.

On the first day of the assembly, 64 public advisers participated. Of these, 37 had been invited through letters sent to randomly selected addresses, and 27 were randomly selected from among those who had registered through open registration. Sixty-three participants attended on the second and third days, and 61 on the fourth day. Fifty-seven public advisers took part in the final vote at the end of the fourth day.

"It is great that citizens have this opportunity to express their opinions, hear the views of others, learn something new, and work towards a shared understanding – a consensus on how to improve their city together."

Tetiana Komareus, participant in the citizens' assembly

Members of the advisory committee, activists, and BRIDGE team representatives on stage at the citizens' assembly, preparing to prioritise recommendations in groups, Zhytomyr, 2 November 2025
Photo: Public Relations Department, Zhytomyr city council

ADVISORY COMMITTEE

The advisory committee of the citizens' assembly was established on 19 July 2025 during the Stakeholder Forum. Its members included three participants nominated by the Zhytomyr city council and 11 self-nominated participants. As a result, a committee of 14 representatives from the public sector, local businesses, educational institutions, and the Zhytomyr city council was formed. Subsequently, during the preparation of the assembly, 12 committee members took an active role:

1. Veronika Boginska
2. Viktor Borshchivsky
3. Volodymyr Didenko
4. Halyna Kyrychuk
5. Zhanna Solovyova
6. Ihor Baranov
7. Kateryna Lozynska
8. Kyrylo Onatsky
9. Maksym Deshkov
10. Oleksandr Kulikov
11. Yulia Hulia
12. Volodymyr Shumlyakivskyi

The advisory committee joined the process as a consultative body, ensuring local legitimacy, thematic relevance, and adherence to the key principles of the assembly. The Committee provided locally informed advice, participated in agenda-setting, and facilitated communication between the project team, the community, and stakeholders.

On the final day of the assembly, representatives of the advisory committee were invited to a dedicated discussion with assembly participants. Nine members of the advisory committee and two representatives of the public who had participated in the preparatory focus groups took part in the discussion. They were asked to assess the feasibility of implementing the developed recommendations in the short term (one to two years) or in the longer term (three years or more). Following the discussion, public advisers in the groups determined the feasibility of each proposal. If half or more of the groups considered a recommendation achievable within one to two years, it was put to a vote.

In the future, the Advisory Committee may play an important role in promoting the implementation of the recommendations of the citizens' assembly in Zhytomyr. In particular, it may provide expert guidance, support communication efforts, and facilitate cooperation with local government bodies.

Public advisors elected as delegates-editors of the citizens' assembly report, Zhytomyr, 2 November 2025
Photo: Ihor Kostash

FEEDBACK FROM ASSEMBLY PARTICIPANTS

Six editors were delegated from among the public advisors to review the report during its preparation, provide comments, and suggest their own additions. They are Mykhailo Rybachuk, Myroslav Vitkovskiy, Oleksandr Rudyk, Viktoria Zahurska-Antoniuk, Svitlana Kovalchuk, and Yaroslav Diatel.

This section was written by the delegated editors as a joint reflection on the process and outcomes of the citizens' assembly.

“Through our participation in the citizens’ assembly held in Zhytomyr in 2025, which addressed issues of transport infrastructure and sustainable mobility in the city, we developed the following view: the assembly was organised and conducted to a very high standard. It is also worth noting the active involvement of city council representatives and the enthusiasm of the citizens who took part.

We believe that such assemblies should not be rare events, but should take place on a regular basis at the initiative of local authorities. They could even be held online, using a dedicated platform where problematic issues are raised, and anyone interested can propose solutions. These proposals could then be reviewed by relevant specialists, with the involvement of independent experts, and efforts made to implement them – rather than merely offering excuses or criticism.

In our view, greater attention should be given at the outset of the assembly to preparatory training sessions for participants. The purpose of these sessions should be to familiarise participants in detail with the procedures and principles of the assembly, as well as to clarify the rules of interaction in group discussions and the logic of decision-making. This is essential to ensure constructive dialogue and a shared focus on common goals, even in situations involving conflicting interests.

A citizens’ assembly is a space for reconciling private and public interests. Through mutual listening, reasoned argument, and the exchange of perspectives, participants learn to transform individual concerns into constructive proposals that take into account the capacities and interests of the community as a whole. What may be convenient or beneficial for a narrow group does not always serve the wider community, and decisions that benefit the community may, in turn, limit opportunities for certain groups. In such cases, seeking compromise is essential.

It is important to involve citizens from all sectors and professions in citizens’ assemblies, taking into account territorial and age diversity.

While the assembly was funded by European donors and organised in line with their principles and vision, we believe it is equally significant to contribute our own perspectives and continue developing this approach locally. If a significant proportion of the population (for example, 30 per cent) were involved in such participatory processes, this could provide an impetus for the emergence of many capable leaders who are ready – and not afraid – to initiate change, improve their communities, and strengthen democracy in society. These individuals would also benefit from strong support from like-minded citizens. A kind of informal “school” for citizens’ assembly participants could help many people learn how to seek solutions to problems, take initiative, act collectively, and move beyond a narrow focus on individual interests.

During the assembly, we observed a strong willingness among citizens to act and to contribute. However, there appears to be a lack of organisers who could bring together groups of like-minded people and guide them towards constructive and positive action.

We would like to express our gratitude to the organisers for the high level of preparation and conduct of the assembly. Also, to the representatives of the Zhytomyr city council and all the speakers for their active participation in the training and presentations. We would also like to thank the citizens who directly participated in the assembly, sacrificing their weekends for the benefit of the community”.

A board displaying the results of the group work submitted for interim voting on the second day of the citizens' assembly, Zhytomyr, 2025. Photo: Ihor Kostash

ASSEMBLY FUNDING

The citizens' assembly in Zhytomyr was organised as a joint initiative of the Zhytomyr city council and the BRIDGE project, which is being implemented with the financial support of the European Union. Zhytomyr was the winning community in an open competition announced by the BRIDGE project in the Kyiv, Chernihiv, and Zhytomyr regions to test the citizens' assembly as an experimental format for public participation.

All expenses related to the preparation and delivery of the assembly were covered by the BRIDGE project budget. This included the involvement of experts, remuneration for facilitators, logistics, technical support, the development of training materials, and compensation for public advisers for their participation across all days of the event. No costs were incurred from the local budget of the Zhytomyr community, which is particularly important given the military-related strain on public finances.

The BRIDGE project is implemented under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (grant agreement No. 101160337). The project aims to strengthen Ukraine's democratic resilience, develop the research capacity of the Kyiv School of Economics, and establish effective links between academic research, public policy, and municipal practice. One of its key areas focuses on the introduction and testing of consultative formats for citizen participation, enabling residents to influence decision-making in complex areas of local politics.

The BRIDGE project is implemented by an international consortium comprising the Kyiv School of Economics (Ukraine), Erasmus University Rotterdam (the Netherlands), the University of Tartu (Estonia), the Technical University of Berlin (Germany), and the Centre for Innovation Development (Ukraine).

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Brochures and the programme for the first day before the start of the citizens' assembly, 25 October 2025, Zhytomyr. Photo: Ihor Kostash

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

In this section, we would like to express our sincere gratitude and pay tribute to all the institutions, teams, and individuals who made the citizens' assembly in Zhytomyr possible and contributed to the achievement of its goals.

In chronological order, we would like to thank the Slavutych city council and the Council of Europe Office in Ukraine for providing the BRIDGE project team with the opportunity to attend the final session of the citizens' assembly in Slavutych. Observing and becoming familiar with the process first-hand was a key step in preparing for the assembly in Zhytomyr.

We would like to thank the Department of Information and Public Relations of the Secretariat of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine – in particular, the Deputy Director of the Department, Nataliia Oksha, and the Deputy Head of the Department, Tetiana Andriychuk – as well as the military administrations of the Zhytomyr, Chernihiv, and Kyiv regions, the Association of Ukrainian Cities (AUC), the All-Ukrainian Association of Territorial Communities, and the news and information portals Decentralisation and RecoveryWindow.

We would like to express our gratitude to the Zviahel city council and the Chernihiv Regional Development Agency for facilitating the information events held in preparation for the assembly.

We would like to express our special gratitude to the Council of Europe Office in Ukraine for its consistent promotion of deliberative approaches and citizens' assemblies in Ukraine, as well as for its participation in the BRIDGE project's information events.

The citizens' assembly in Zhytomyr was made possible primarily thanks to the active and responsible participation of the Zhytomyr city council. Representatives of the city council promptly prepared the competition application and worked closely with the BRIDGE project team at all stages of the assembly's preparation and implementation, providing necessary information, coordinating interdepartmental cooperation, and preparing materials.

We would like to express our special gratitude to Halyna Shymanska, acting mayor of Zhytomyr, Svitlana Olshanska, first deputy mayor, and Oleksandr Shevchuk, deputy mayor for executive bodies, for their comprehensive support in organising the assembly. It is also important to note that key coordination on behalf of the Zhytomyr city council was carried out by the teams led by Borys Pakholiuk at the municipal institution City Development Agency and by Olha Akhmedova in the public relations department.

We would like to express our special gratitude to the active residents and community activists of Zhytomyr, whose involvement at all stages of the assembly's preparation made the process truly collaborative. Their participation in selecting the theme and working with the advisory committee and focus groups to shape the agenda played a key role in ensuring that the assembly reflected the city's real needs and remained relevant to the community.

We express our sincere gratitude to Polissia National University, and personally to its rector, professor of economics Oleh Skidan, for providing the venue, technical support, and equipment that made it possible to hold the citizens' assembly over four days.

An integral part of the event was the facilitation process – supporting participants, organising discussions, and creating a safe space for dialogue. We therefore extend our sincere gratitude to the team of facilitators who carried out this important work: Nataliia Velychko,

Mariia Hryshchenko, Nataliia Malynovska, Yuliia Matviichuk, Olha Palkova-Svirchevska, Vitalina Popova, Tetiana Terletska, and Danylo Yashchuk.

The BRIDGE project team involved in the preparation and delivery of the citizens' assembly in Zhytomyr included Oleksandra Keudel, Kerstin Luker, Illia Tkachenko, Anastasiia Tereshchuk, Elvira Podolska, and professor Hans-Ludger Dinkel. We also extend our special thanks to project researchers Tetiana Lukeria and Andrii Darkovych for analysing and documenting the experience of the Zhytomyr assembly, to Olha Kram for preparing visual materials, and to Viktoriia Krechko for coordinating participant communications.

An important part of the assembly was its educational component, and we are sincerely grateful to all the experts who devoted their time and shared their knowledge and experience with the participants.

We would like to thank photographer Ihor Kostash and videographers Yuliia Parukh and Oleh Rohov for documenting the four intensive days of the assembly and helping to preserve this experience for a wider audience.

Special thanks go to Anastasiia Shemchuk and Oleh Klimov from WellDone for providing translation and technical support for the online presentations by speakers from Barcelona and Taiwan, making these contributions accessible to all assembly participants.

We would also like to thank the catering contractor Oksana Samchuk and the Poliskyi Smak canteen for the excellent food and high-quality service provided throughout the assembly.

ПОЛІСЬКИЙ
НАЦІОНАЛЬНИЙ
УНІВЕРСИТЕТ

KSE Arte

BRIDGE

Building P
Innovation
Governan

Окі

Університетський Об'єднаний Студентський Центр у Львові спільно з "Полісським Національним Університетом" організує конкурс на виконання проекту "BRIDGE" (Містко) на території Львівської області. Конкурс проводиться у рамках проекту "BRIDGE" (Містко) у рамках програми "Полісський Національний Студентський Центр у Львові".

TAK	30

Final voting of the public assembly,
November 2, 2025, Zhytomyr
Photo: Ihor Kostash